

Formulation And Evaluation of Polyherbal Cookies for Diabetics

Sonawane Sneha*

Vidya Niketan Institute of Pharmacy and Research Centre Bota.

ABSTRACT

Most of the people consume cookies during their breakfast, snacks and leisure time to regulate their hunger and get some energy, in market there are varieties of cookies which are available, and the main components are refined flour, sugar and butter. Hence, are generally avoided by obese and diabetic patients as they lead to high sugar level in blood. Therefore, in this recent investigation, we have formulated Polyherbal cookies using oats, wheat flour and different Ayurveda herb. Diverse varieties were formulated using different plant to find out the best composition for cookies on the basis of palatability. After selection, cookies were formulated for the physiochemical, sensory and their nutritional analysis. Sensory analysis was evaluated based on organoleptic characteristics: color, taste, aroma and overall acceptability on the basis of 9-paledonic scale. Physiochemical evaluation including: total ash value, total moisture content total water and alcoholic extraction, total moisture content. On the basis of its nutritional value comparison, it was found that the protein content is higher in our formulation than the other marketed preparation.

Keywords: refined flour, sugar and butter.

INTRODUCTION

Plants have provided a source of inspiration for novel drug compounds, as plant derived medicines have made large contributions of human health and well-being. Traditional medicine using plant extract continues to provide health coverage for over 80% of the world's population, especially in the developing world. Plants are used medicinally in different countries and are a source of many potent and powerful drugs. Medicinal plants provide good remedies for human diseases and play a vital role in our day-to-day life. Indian systems of medicines are all based on the knowledge of drugs from plants. Higher plants, as sources of medicinal compounds, have continued to play a dominant role in the maintenance of human health since ancient time. Over 50% of all modern clinical drugs are natural product origin and natural products play an important role in drug development programs in the pharmaceutical industry. In India people have been used plants and natural products for the treatment of various diseases from ancient time. In the last two decades of the century the scientists are sincerely trying to evaluate

many plant drugs used in traditional system of medicine. [1] Diabetes- common, non-communicable metabolic disorder mostly occurring in young ones and are associated with other diseases like kidney disease, cardiovascular diseases etc. It occurs when pancreas does not produce insulin or is not properly consumed by body. According to the WHO survey report globally, it is estimated that 422 million adults were suffering in 2014 and rate of increment is about from 4.7% to 8.5%. Diabetes mellitus, a chronic metabolic disease condition enounces by the elevated glucose level in blood (Hyperglycemia), hyperlipidemia, negative nitrogen balance, glycosuria and sometimes ketonemia. Basically, it is grouped in three main types: Type-1 diabetes mellitus / Insulin dependent diabetes mellitus/Juvenile onset diabetes mellitus, which are mostly caused by the T-cell mediated autoimmune devastation of islets of insulin secretion Beta cells. Type-2diabetes mellitus /Non-Insulin Dependent diabetes mellitus occurs due to the moderate reduction in β cell mass or the low circulation of insulin due to the interaction of genetic or metabolic factor. Nearly 90% of diabetes patients are suffering from type-2 diabetes. And Type-3

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occurred during pregnancy when insulin is not produced properly or the cells become resist to insulin. Insulin is a hypoglycemic hormone with two polypeptide 51 amino acid chains. 1U insulin is secreted per hour by the human pancreas but maximum amount is being secreted after meal and are controlled by chemical, hormonal and neural mechanism. Insulin is site specific and is present on all cell membrane but more densely depends on the cell type: liver and fat cells are rich in its presence. Some of the secondary messenger like PIP3 activate PI3 kinase also facilitates the action of insulin on metabolism enzymes. Insulin activates glucose transport through the cell membrane by ATP dependent transfer of glucose transporter (GLUT-4) to plasma membrane. The secondary messenger PIP3 and certain tyrosine phosphorylated guanine exchanger protein help GLUT-4 to move from cytosol to the plasma membrane. Recent drugs which are used to treat diabetes worldwide are in effect, but some natural therapies, natural foods and various changes in the lifestyle would be a wise act to treat and control diabetes and its associated disease. Various plants, its part or products (more than 1200) are identified as hypoglycemic with fewer side effect. Polyherbal antidiabetic cookies are the combination of various herbs and cereals that have a great power to stimulate insulin secretion by countless mechanism of action. These cookies contain oats, *Tecoma stans* leaves, Tulsi leaves, ashwagandha, honey, artificial sugar (sucralose) etc., which is tasty, healthy as well as beneficial for a diabetic patient of all age group and as the product contains herbs and cereals it has less adverse effect on one's body. According to WHO report, 2016 it was made an action plan for the year from 2013-2020 in which it involved various action plans and suggested natural food products which can decrease or regularise the blood glucose level in blood should be developed more.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

- **Aim :**

The aim of the present study is to design and formulate a cookie formulation as a drug delivery system for diabetic patients.

- **Objective :**

- The objective of the study is to design polyherbal cookies containing *Tecoma stans*, Tulsi leaves and ashwagandha.
- The essential target of the study was to formulate and evaluate antidiabetic polyherbal cookies that will have to work on antidiabetic enhancing property.
- Polyherbal formulation has wide therapeutic range, pure side effects, cheaper eco-friendly and rapidly available.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 A Complete Review on *Avena sativa* :

Kinthali Usha Rani *et al*, (2021),

The review of all clinical results study *Avena sativa* a potential candidate as nutraceutical & pharmaceutical agent. The advantages seen within clinical studies, but it must be well tried in larger studies for further exploration within therapeutic aspect would be helpful.

1.2 Evaluation of the Cookies Formulated with *Costus igneus* Plant Material for Antidiabetic Activity :

A Rajani Chowdary *et al*, (2020),

The present research work aimed to formulate a nutritionally rich cookie with *Costus igneus* leaf extract and to determine the effect of cookie consumption on decreasing blood glucose level in type 2 Diabetic patient.

1.3 Therapeutic Properties and Applications of *Tecoma stans* Linn :

Abisha Vince Jeo V.S *et al*, (2020),

In the recent study, the researcher gave the evidence that it contains chemical constituents like alkaloids, amino acids, phytosterols, monoterpenes, triterpenes, glycosides and phenols, tannins, saponin & flavonoids. The present review comprises the

pharmacological, phytochemical & therapeutic potential of *Tecoma stans*.

1.4 Formulation of Polyherbal Antidiabetic Cookies :

Kajal Pathak *et al*, (2018),

The cookies are generally avoided by obese and diabetic patients as they cause high sugar level in blood. So, objective of present research was to formulate polyherbal Cookies with the help of oats, wheat flour & different Ayurvedic Herbs.

1.5 Phytopharmacology of Ashwagandha as an Anti-Diabetic Herb :

Vikas Kumar *et al*, (2017),

The study aimed to focus on Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) extract & several pharmaceutical formulations containing them are currently often used as tonics useful for prevention and cure of mental health problems including sleep disturbances, accompanying chronic diseases. The *W. Somnifera* could be used for treatment of diabetes associated with metabolic disturbances.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Table No 1. List of ingredients used

Name of ingredients	Sources
<i>Tecoma stans</i>	Local area, Sangamner
Ashwagandha	VNIPRC Bota
Tulsi	VNIPRC Bota
Oats	Local market, Sakur
Milk	Local market, Sakur
Flavoring Agents	Local market, Sakur
Tupe (Homemade)	Local market, Sakur
Salt	Local market, Sakur
Baking soda	Local market, Sakur
Baking powder	Local market, Sakur
Artificial sugar	Diabliss Local area, Sangamner
Wheat flour	Local market, Sakur

Table No 2. list of equipments used

Name of Equipment	Make/Mode
Digital Weighing Balance	VNIPRC
Soxhlet Apparatus	VNIPRC
Hot Air Oven	VNIPRC
Desiccator	VNIPRC

Method of Preparation :-

Preparation of Cookies :-

Different compositions of cookies were formulated using different ratios of Oats, wheat flour, roasted, *Tecoma stans* leaves powder, Ashwagandha powder, Tulsi powder, Milk, Flavoring agent (vanilla), salt, baking powder, baking soda, tupe, artificial sugar (sugar free Natura), and based on the palatability and visual appealing final product were selected for sensory evaluation and nutritional value.

Figure 5. Preparation of cookie

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

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7. Phytochemical Evaluation of Powdered Flower Extract of *Tecoma stans* :-

The powdered flower sample of *Tecoma stans* was taken and phytochemical screening was done to check the phytoconstituents present using standard reagents.

a) Carbohydrates :-

Molisch's test:

About 2ml of powdered flower extract was mixed with 0.2 ml of alcoholic solution of α -naphthol 10% in addition to 2 ml of sulphuric acid, a bluish violet

zone is formed this indicates the presence of carbohydrates and /or glycosides.

b) Alkaloids :-

About 0.2 g of the powdered flower extracts was warmed with 2% H₂S₀₄ for two minutes. It was filtered and few drops of Dragendroff's reagent were added. Orange red precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

c) Tannins :-

Small quantity of powdered flower extract was mixed with water and heated on water bath. The mixture was filtered and ferric chloride was added to the filtrate. A dark green solution indicates the presence of tannins.

d) Glycosides :-

The powdered flower extract was hydrolysed with HCl solution and neutralized with NaOH solution. A few drops of Fehling's solution A and B were added. Red precipitate indicates the presence of glycosides.

e) Saponins :-

About 0.2 g of the powdered flower extract was shaken with 5ml of distilled water and then heated to boil. Frothing (Appearance of creamy miss of small bubbles) shows the presence of saponins.

f) Flavonoids :-

Powdered flower extract of about 0.2 g was dissolved in diluted NaOH and HCl was added. A yellow solution that turns colourless, indicates the presence of flavonoids.

g) Steroids (LB test) :-

2 ml of acetic anhydride was added to 0.5 g of the powdered flower of each with 2 ml of H₂ S₀₄. The colour changed from violet to blue or green in samples indicating the presence of steroids.

h) Proteins :-

To the powdered flower extract, 5%NaOH and 1% copper sulphate solution were added. Violet color produced shows the presence of proteins.

i) Amino acids :-

The powdered flower was treated with Million's reagent. Red colour showed the presence of amino acids.

j) Phenolic compounds :-

Small quantities of powdered flower samples were taken separately in water and test for the presence of phenolic compounds was carried out by using reagents like 5%ferric chloride solution, 1%gelatin solution containing 10% NaCl and 10%lead acetate.

k) Gums and Mucilage :-

A small quantity of powdered flower extracts were added separately to 25ml of absolute alcohol with stirring and filtered. The precipitate was dried in air and examined for its swelling properties. No swelling was observed indicates the absence of gums and mucilage.

RESULTS

Sr. No	Evaluation Parameter	F1	F2	F3
1.	Appearance	Soft Cookies	Soft Cookies	Soft Cookies
2.	Colour	Yellowish Green	Yellowish Green And Red	Light Yellow And Red
3.	Order	Pleasant Herbal Odour	Pleasant Smell	Mild Herbal Smell
4.	Consistency	Good	Very good	Good
5.	Spreadability	6.8 g.cm/sec	7.5 g.cm/sec	6.5 g.cm/sec
6.	Stability Study	Stable	Stable	Stable
7	Wieght Of Cookies	70 gm	80gm	75 gm

Sr. no	Chemical and physiochemical parameters	Results
1	Ash content	7.10%
2	Moisture content	6.91%
3	Alkaloid	Present
4	Alcohol extraction	6.58%
5	Water extraction	5.30%
6	Fat content	14.04%
7	Carbohydrate content	60.51%
8	Protein content	11.65%
9	Total energy	414.9874 Kcal

By above mentioned Table 1 of results shown, those Cookies were spanning in nutritional values with controlled fat and carbohydrate and high rich in protein content which have made it acceptable among the health-conscious people, growing people and case of malnutrition. Comparative studies of different parameters of sensory evaluation exhibited that use of curry leaves as an active ingredient has given an appetizing and flavoring effect. Selected composition of cookies has made it acceptable around 90-96% that will give us a hope to convert this formulation into large scale production. In terms of physiochemical properties, nutrition value, sensory evaluation and comparison with other marketed product were in acceptable range.

DISCUSSION

Aroma and Color :-

Aroma or fragrance of foods are the indiscernible part of the acceptance and play a crucial role in mouth feel. Aroma is the first sign of consumer to choose any food for consumption as well as color of food product is a sign of acceptance that have a great impact on the choice of any product. Aroma and color show an elegant effect on the acceptance. The outcome of results showed that strong combined *Tecoma stans* leaves, Ashwagandha and Tulsi powder's aroma influenced the people greatly.

Overall Acceptance of Cookies

It is very important for food, snacks, and soft drinks that after taking the bite or ship it must give a palatable and flavourful effect on tongue so it could be taken easily. The results of sensory evaluation on

the basis of taste, flavour, crispiness and aroma were found to be appreciable with medicated effect.

Flavour

Flavour is an integral part of taste that plays a vital role in the acceptance of any food material. Used flavour of *Tecoma stans* leaves and coco was found to be highly appreciable among all the volunteer of sensory evaluation because its smell act as an appetizer, because of that it means score on excel was found to be 90-95%

Sensory Evaluation

Taste is a strategic parameter of sensory evaluation. The product might be captivating and having an eminent energy but sans of righteous taste it is likely to unaccepted. So, on the basis of sensory evaluation, it is found that due to use of *Tecoma stans* leaves its mean score was 90-95% among the age group of 18-40. Graph of taste has been depicted below.

CONCLUSION

- **Successful Formulation:** Created a palatable snack by blending specific anti-diabetic herbs Tecoma Stans, Tulsi, Ashwagandha into a low-glycemic, sugar-free cookie base.
- **Therapeutic Potential:** The integration Tecoma Stans, Tulsi, Ashwagandha of polyherbal ingredients offers natural support for blood glucose regulation.
- **Nutritional Value:** Provides a healthier, nutrient-dense alternative to conventional bakery products.
- **Future Scope:** These cookies serve as a viable prototype for commercial functional foods aimed at natural diabetes management.

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